

Test Cases and Test Case Profiles for consistent documentation of complex multi-sector experiments

Smart energy systems are complex, incorporating multiple sectors, including power systems, heating and cooling, and communications. Documenting experiments consisting of multiple domains includes added complexity and interdependencies between the domains, which should be identified. At the same time, experts in one domain are reaching the cap and experimenting with interdisciplinary systems. Identifying pools of relevant interdisciplinary experiments is increasingly crucial.

Figure 1 Holistic Test Description

Holistic Test Description

Holistic Test Description is a structured approach developed to support designing and documenting complex multi-domain experiments. This approach divides experiments into test case, test specification, and experimental specification. Holistic Test Description was initially developed in ERIGRID project and has been extended and updated in ERIGRID 2.0 project.

Domain Under Investigation Control Electrical Power Heating/Cooling ICT Market Mechanical Thermal	Type of Assessment Device Compliance Verification Functional Performance Technical Feasibility Controller Conflicts Interoperability Testing ICT Failure Impacts Configuration Failure Impact Cyber-security Performance / Resilience Control System Functional Verification Fault Condition Normal Condition Communication Performance Protection Equipment Response Characterisation Verification Validation Device Testing Software Testing Algorithm Testing DER aggregate Microgrid Local Energy Community Low Voltage Grid Medium Voltage Grid High Voltage Grid Gas Network Energy Market Communication Infrastructure ICT Aggregation Platform Control Devices / IED DMS / EMS / SCADA DER Controller Energy Market Agents DER Heat Consumer Sector Coupling Component Heat Storage
Tested phenomenon Transient Response Frequency Stability Short Circuit Behaviour Rotor Angle Stability Congestion Power Balance Energy Balance Ancillary Services Fault Event Sequence Cascading Failure Communication Phenomena Voltage Stability Voltage Quality Harmonic Distortion Harmonic Stability Small-signal Stability Sector Coupling Economic Performance Package Loss Cyber-security Events Communication Delays Communication Congestion	Test System / components DER aggregate Microgrid Local Energy Community Low Voltage Grid Medium Voltage Grid High Voltage Grid Gas Network Energy Market Communication Infrastructure ICT Aggregation Platform Control Devices / IED DMS / EMS / SCADA DER Controller Energy Market Agents DER Heat Consumer Sector Coupling Component Heat Storage

Figure 2 Test Case Profile keywords

Test Case Profiles

Test Case Profiles group together test cases based on keywords (see Figure 2), enabling pools of test cases on specified domains. Users of the Test Case Profiles can dynamically pick keywords suitable for their needs and find a pool of test cases with these keywords.

Figure 3 Examples of Test Case Profiles

Further Reading

Existing test cases and test case profiles are available on ERIGRID 2.0 GitHub repository.